

Final Report - TAG C: FAIR Resources and Training for Researchers

July 2018

Executive Summary:

The FAIR Resources and Training for Researchers Targeted Adoption Group (herein, TAG C) was formed by key stakeholders of the Enabling FAIR Data Project to guide key liaison individuals (e.g., librarians, journal editors, funders/program officers, repository managers) to existing educational resources / training on achieving more FAIR data practices, to inform their decision-making and to bring back to their communities of researchers. Noting the potential for significant change in the publishing and repository ecosystem when implementing the FAIR data principles, project stakeholders determined that without training and support, changes in policy or procedure cannot be well understood and therefore, may be enacted poorly. Given the timeframe for the Enabling FAIR project, TAG C organizers decided to expend their efforts on consolidating existing educational resources rather than re-inventing them, and using existing mechanisms for curating those resources, i.e., the ESIP-hosted Data Management Training Clearinghouse (DMTC) at <http://dmtraining.esipfed.org>. Target audiences for the educational resources were determined to be 1) researchers in the Earth and Space Sciences who need to understand FAIR data principles and 2) the data professionals who support them by providing training on research data management (RDM) practices and skills development.

In order to achieve their objectives, TAG C organizers decided to use several crowdsourcing events to: first, identify educational resources that could provide guidance to their target audiences about enabling FAIR data principles, and secondly, map those identified resources to the FAIR data principles and sub-principles themselves. The events proved to be both collaborative and innovative based on participant feedback, and successfully identified and FAIR-mapped a number of unique resources that will be added to the DMTC during the implementation phase of the Enabling FAIR project. This report provides analyses of 1) the crowdsourcing events as means of raising awareness of new concepts (such as the FAIR Data principles) and services (such as the DMTC), 2) the resources identified, and 3) the mapping efforts. Finally, recommendations are included to support other TAG deliverables, and for processes to facilitate the implementation efforts of the Enabling FAIR project.

Introduction:

Organizing Team:

Nancy Hoebelheinrich, Knowledge Motifs LLC, Co-Chair with Jonathan Petters, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University; Raleigh Martin, AAAS Science & Technology Policy Fellow hosted at the U.S. National Science Foundation, Sophie Hou, University Corporation for Atmospheric research/National Center for Atmospheric Research, Leslie Hsu, U.S. Geological Survey, Eric Olson, ORCID, Rowena Davis, Belmont Forum e-Infrastructures and Data Management.

Working Group Purpose

The concept of making research data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to promote research reproducibility, and research data sharing and re-use (Wilkinson et al., 2016), has caught the attention of researchers and research stakeholders in many fields (e.g., NIH Data Commons Pilot Phase, 2018; Mons et al., 2017).

Kicking off in Fall 2017, the Enabling FAIR Data Project aims to “align publishers and repositories in following best practices to enable FAIR data and to create workflows so that researchers will have a simplified, common experience when submitting their paper to any leading Earth and space science journal” (Stall et al., 2017).

Several Targeted Adoption Groups (TAGs) formed as a means to accomplish this project’s goals. These groups focused on developing recommendations for key stakeholders such as publishers, repositories, and funders to harmonize actions among different groups toward making data FAIR. These TAGs included the groups “Repository Guidance for Researchers,” “Culture Change through Credit,” and “Publishers in the Earth and Space Science Team.”

To support the implementation of FAIR data recommendations from these TAGs, stakeholders from the Enabling FAIR Data project deemed it vital that relevant training and guidance be available to publishers, repositories, funders, and researchers in the Earth and Space Sciences (ESS). Without training and support, changes in policy or procedure cannot be well understood and therefore, may be enacted poorly. Thus a TAG called “FAIR Resources and Training for Researchers,” known herein as TAG C, was formed for the following purpose (*slightly edited in this manuscript*):

“Guide key liaison individuals (e.g., librarians, journal editors, funders/program officers, repository managers) to existing educational resources / training on achieving more FAIR data practices to inform their decision-making and to bring back to their communities of researchers.”

Target Audiences for Resources

Many stakeholders (e.g., researchers, research support, data repository managers, publishers, editors, funders, etc.) could benefit from connections to or development of data management training material. This TAG chose to limit the scope of its work to providing guidance for a) researchers and b) parties who provide research data management (RDM) training or policy guidance to researchers (i.e., ‘train the trainers’).

This TAG coalesced its efforts around the Data Management Training Clearinghouse (DMTC), a currently existing registry for online research data management learning resources hosted by the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP). Much of the TAG’s effort focused upon identifying existing data management training resources that can be added to the DMTC and mapping those resources to the FAIR principles as described in Wilkinson et al. (2016).

Relationships with other Working Groups

In the spirit of the Enabling FAIR data project, TAG C leveraged its efforts as much as possible on existing resources and activities. In addition to direct collaboration with the ESIP DMT Working Group, TAG C also worked closely with related efforts being organized by the Research Data Alliance (RDA), the Belmont Forum e-Infrastructures & Data Management (BF e-I&DM) activity, and other working groups within ESIP. TAG C also maintained close connections to other AGU FAIR Targeted Adoption Groups. For example, TAG G, which liaises with several international efforts to define standards for actionable data management plans (DMPs), has closely consulted with TAG C on identifying training resources to support DMP best practices by researchers.

Working Group Deliverables:

Educational and Training Resources Identified for Researchers

The Enabling FAIR Data Project, the DMTC, and the ongoing drive to improve research data infrastructure and resources are cross-sector community efforts. Data management training materials are also created and shared by a wide variety of organizations around the globe, but these resources are often difficult to locate, and therefore, re-use, due to widespread and disparate distribution mechanisms. In order to begin centralizing and describing these resources, TAG C invited the data management community to a series of crowdsourcing virtual meetings. These events are adapted from similar efforts in the open science community, particularly the Mozilla Study Groups.

Crowdsourcing event overview

Two crowdsourcing events were organized and hosted on ESIP's online meeting and webinar platform. Adapted from the format preferred by the Study Groups community run by Mozilla, each event encourages simultaneous learning and collaboration (2018). A session begins with a project leader or expert contextualizing the task for the call, while a moderator shares questions from the participants. The first event facilitated interested participants' searches for and identification of educational and training resources to add to the DMT Clearinghouse that could help enable researchers to make their data FAIR. The second event mapped the resources that were found in the first crowdsourcing event to the FAIR principles, and prepared them to be added to the DMT Clearinghouse. Both events were scheduled for an hour and 15 minutes, with the second event scheduled at a time that better accommodated participants from the southern continents (including Australia). Background information for each event shared with participants can be found on Google Drive at: [Event #1](#) and [Event #2](#).

Additional goals for the two events were the same:

- Develop awareness of the FAIR Data Principles, the Enabling FAIR Data project, and the Data Management Training Clearinghouse
- Contribute to the inventory of educational resources related to RDM with a focus on Enabling the FAIR data principles, and
- Generate broader, engaged participation for both projects

Crowdsourcing was chosen as a method of identifying educational and training resources for several reasons. First, the TAG C group members thought that such events could be organized fairly rapidly; this was an important consideration given the relatively short time-frame of approximately 7 months which the Enabling FAIR Data project had allocated to accomplish the first phase of its work (i.e., identifying the problems associated with enabling FAIR data for researchers, and making recommendations on how to approach / solve these problems). Secondly, a crowdsourcing event had the potential to bring together a wide range of experts from many subject disciplines within the Earth and Space Sciences who had a wide variety of roles and responsibilities associated with the research lifecycle. Those differing backgrounds promised the opportunity to greatly expand TAG C's understanding of the breadth of approaches to the Enabling FAIR Data and RDM training resources that could be found. Thirdly, bringing these RDM experts to the table provided another way to raise the awareness of the Enabling FAIR project efforts and the DMTC. In this way, the crowdsourcing events themselves became teaching and learning opportunities. The crowdsourcing events proved to be helpful and productive toward what TAG C accomplished during the project timeline.

Crowdsourcing events were advertised to a wide variety of audiences associated with Earth and Space Science informatics. The list of organizations and listservs to which notice of the events was sent is included in Appendix A, Table 1. For each event, notices were sent to invite people

to register, and then sent again closer to the event to remind participants to register and/or attend the events.

Resource Identification (Crowdsource event #1)

On February 22, 2018, a group of 28 data management training (DMT) stakeholders gathered through the GoToWebinar platform to collaboratively crowdsource DMT materials. After introductions, participants received brief information about the Enabling FAIR Data project (see Erin Robinson slides at: [Project Overview Slides](#)), and the selection criteria for the DMTC (see Nancy Hoebelheinrich slides at: [Selecting Resources for the DMTC](#)). Then, participants were introduced to three organizing frameworks for their searches: (1) An example of a research data lifecycle (Faundeen et al., 2013) (2) the FAIR Guiding Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), and (3) skills development that focused more broadly on foundational data management principles. The participants, composed primarily of librarians and data experts, were drawn from data communities including ESIP, the Enabling AGU FAIR Data Project, ORCID, USGS Community for Data Integration (CDI), Belmont Forum e-Infrastructure & Data Management Initiative, EarthCube, and Cyverse. The participants were then invited to self-organize into three groups according to the three organizing frameworks. Using the EtherPad collaborative discussion platform and associated Google Sheets, each group identified a series of appropriate resources to add to the DMTC (26, 15, and 37 entries for Groups 1-3, respectively). Upon identification, participants entered basic information for the RDM resources, using a subset of the metadata scheme used by the DMT Clearinghouse (the Learning Resource Metadata Initiative schema, LRMI, maintained by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative). Basic information that was gathered for each resource included title, URL, resource type, a narrative description and notes.

Spreadsheet of Identified Resources

The full list of identified resources, separated by organizing framework, can be found on [Google Sheets](#). In the post-event analysis of Crowdsource event #1, TAG C organizers decided that the triad of organizing frameworks was useful for gathering resources, but might not be as useful for mapping training resources to the FAIR principles. Therefore, all identified resources were aggregated into a single list, which can also be found on [Google Sheets](#). After eliminating duplicates, this aggregated list of 78 unique resources was then used as the starting point for the second “mapping” crowdsource event.

Resource Mapping (Crowdsource event #2)

The second crowdsourcing event occurred on March 29, 2018, shortly after the Enabling FAIR Stakeholder meeting held in Potsdam, Germany in conjunction with RDA Plenary 11. This event was intended to map resources identified in the first crowdsourcing event to FAIR principles. As before, participants registered using a Google form; of the 23 registered, 9 attended; an additional 8 attended who had not previously registered (total attendance ~ 17). After an explanation of the purpose and workflow planned for the event, participants were shown examples of educational resources that had been chosen and how they could be mapped to the FAIR Data Principles (see Nancy Hoebelheinrich slides at: [Examples of](#)

[Educational Resources & Mapping to FAIR](#)). Participants then had 45 minutes to map the resources they had chosen from the aggregated list of resources using the Google Form prepared for that purpose ([Mapping Educational Resources on Research Data Management \(RDM\) to the FAIR Data Principles](#)).

Analysis

Range & type of contributors

Crowdsource Event #1: At the time of this event, there were 38 pre-registered participants and 8 additional participants who joined without filling out the registration questionnaire. Appendix A Table 2A shows their self-declared areas of expertise (participants were allowed to choose more than one). The area of expertise most common among participants was “Data professional (supporting the data processing workflow).”

Crowdsource Event #2: The total number of participants who self-declared their presence at Event #2 was 17, with 6 more people attending than registered. Of those registered, 30 percent had attended the first crowdsourcing event. As with the first event, registrants were asked to self-declare their areas of expertise using set categories, with multiple responses allowed. By far, the largest areas of expertise declared by the registrants were in the “data repository,” “data professionals supporting the data processing workflow,” and “data management educator” areas. See Appendix A. Table 2a for full details.

While the registration and participant sign-in forms for crowdsource event #2 did not ask for a categorization of the organizations represented, it appears that the representation from both pre-registrants and participants included primarily academic and government participants, as well as some people from non-profit and industry. See Appendix A. Table 2b.

Educational & training resources identified

Details of the identified resources categorized by organizing framework and resource format / media type are provided in Appendix A. Table 3. In brief, more resources were identified using the third approach (Skills Development related to RDM), than the other approaches, i.e., 37 out of the total 78 resources identified. Following fairly closely was the first approach (Research Data Lifecycle), i.e., 26 out of 78. The second approach (FAIR Data Principles) seemed the most elusive for the participants, with 15 out of 78 resources identified. Some of those resources identified were published papers on topics related to the FAIR Data principles, however, and would not be considered educational or training resources via the selection criteria for the DMTC. Per that selection criteria, this type of information would, instead, be resources that could be included in “pathfinders” or “bibliographies” or other reference materials that could be usefully included in an educational / training resource such a full course or shorter tutorial.

In terms of the resource format or media identified, the most frequently identified format was the “text” format which included web pages, websites, and PDFs, i.e., 37 out of 78. The second most frequently identified format was “Presentations” which usually included downloadable presentation slides in a format such as MS Powerpoint or PDF. Note that some of these resources may, upon submission to the DMTC, be assigned other format types than those assigned during the crowdsourcing event. For example, some resources considered “texts” could instead be considered “events” such as webinars and other representations of timed occasions when training took place rather than the “text” format. Appendix A. Table 3 includes a column denoting the number of resources per format type after review by DMTC reviewers / editors. The [reference sheet](#) defines the formats and types of resources submitted.

Mapping of FAIR resources

During the second crowdsourcing event, 31 of the total 78 submitted resources were mapped to the FAIR data principles using the form found at: [Mapping Educational Resources on Research Data Management \(RDM\) to the FAIR Data Principles](#). We asked mappers to identify how resources related to specific elements of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Detailed responses are provided in Appendix B. The full response can also be found at: [Mapping Responses](#). As a brief summary:

Findable

- Most of the resources mapped to the Findable data principle;
- F4 (metadata specify the data identifiers) was least covered of the four sub-principles, thus revealing a Findable topic that should be included in future educational resources.

Accessible

- The identified resources covered fewer of the Accessible principles in general with the biggest gap of coverage being principle A2 (metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available).
- The lack of assignment to this sub-principle could be a result of a lack of understanding about what “accessibility” means and how to achieve it with data; if so, the inclusion of more comprehensive explanations and illustration would be warranted, thus showing a clear gap in how these principles could be better covered by existent, adapted and new educational resources.

Interoperable

- Mapping for the sub-principles of the Interoperable principle in general revealed rather less than adequate coverage, with the most coverage for I1 ((meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation) when mapping was applicable. This area could also benefit from more explicit explanation in existent, adapted and new educational resources.

Reusable

- Many of the resources identified and mapped were targeted to specific domain disciplines, so the largely positive coverage of sub-principle R3 ((meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards) is not surprising.

- Resources that were more general in nature often required the mapper to make an assumption that the focus of the resources was on re-usability per comments like the following from the Comments / Questions section for Re-usability:
 - “No sections explicitly address these, but I think the general principles discussed are geared toward reusability.”

Opportunities and challenges associated with interactive format

Participants were able to ask questions and discuss issues that arose with each other and with the organizers in Event #1 via Chat in the Etherpad spaces while they worked on contributing resources to the spreadsheet. The few participants (<10) who used this feature used it as a platform for questions. Inquiries included:

- Whether resources should be considered appropriate for the desired purposes
- The granularity at which resources should be noted and submitted (e.g., modules in a course vs. a course itself)
- What kinds of notes would be most useful to enter

One participant noted that there are many different Data Lifecycle models, not just the USGS life cycle used in the exercise, thus other lifecycle approaches should be considered. Another comment was that “I think explaining the meaning of "FAIR" should actually be considered an element of data management training.”

After Crowdsourcing Event #1, a survey was deployed to solicit feedback on the event. Although only 7 responses were gathered, all respondents had positive comments about the live, collaborative and innovative nature of the event. One respondent commented that they most liked that the event meant time was dedicated specifically to the shared tasks without distraction from other tasks. Another appreciated the fact that people could collaborate, but without speaking; another found the event was an innovative way to get people to work together. There were suggestions for improvements in the technical infrastructure used for the event, but a very large majority of the respondents indicated that they would be interested in participating in other crowdsourcing events. The full results of the survey are described in Appendix C.

During and after Crowdsourcing Event #2, feedback from both participants and organizers noted that the actual work involved in mapping resources to the FAIR Data principles was a complex task that was potentially more easily and accurately done by the creators of the educational resources rather than someone coming to the task who was not as familiar with the resource. In addition, many of the educational resources identified were about metadata and metadata standards. The mapping of these resources to the FAIR principles would probably best be done by those more intimately familiar with the metadata standards being discussed. Any of these kinds of mapping activities would also have to be predicated upon a very good understanding of the FAIR principles themselves. A more complete discussion of the issues raised related to the mapping activity can be found in Appendix D.

Submission to DMTC of resources identified and mapped

One of the associated goals of the TAG C group was to add to the inventory and description of the educational resources in the ESIP-hosted DMTC. At the time of the writing of this Final Report for the first phase of the Enabling FAIR Data project, the educational resources found and mapped during the crowdsourcing activities have not yet been added to the DMTC. The submission of all the resources to the DMTC that meet the selection criteria will happen during the implementation phase of the Enabling FAIR Data project.

Following the submission process, a more comprehensive gap analysis will be possible than the TAG C group was able to do during the first phase, since only about half of the resources identified were mapped to the FAIR principles during the second crowdsourcing event. One of the advantages of adding these resources to the DMTC is its built-in capability to associate educational “frameworks” to the resources submitted, and thus provide a filter or search facet for those resources in the DMTC. An educational framework has now been added to the DMTC for the FAIR Data principles. As a result, upon submission, the TAG C-identified resources will be associated with the FAIR data framework while those identified, but already present in the DMTC (i.e., duplicates) will also be associated with that framework, thus making the resources easier to find for those wishing to learn about the FAIR principles.

Recommended next steps

Recommendations to support TAG deliverables

In addition to the plans already identified for submitting crowdsource event-identified training resources to the DMTC and identifying gaps in these resources, we believe it is also important to identify and map resources that will support the deliverables of other TAGs associated with the Enabling FAIR project. Below, we offer several specific recommendations that align with the idea of “training the trainers”:

- The Enabling FAIR Data effort is drafting a [Commitment Statement](#) on “Enabling FAIR Data in the Earth and Space Sciences.” This statement includes principles for repositories, publishers, societies and institutions, and individual researchers to support and promulgate FAIR data principles. Training resources are essential for all of these stakeholders to be able to meet the goals of the Commitment Statement. Efforts should be made to identify resources tailored to each of these stakeholder groups.
- More specific to publishers, the Enabling FAIR Data draft “[Author Guidelines](#)” provide specific recommendations for how journals can encourage/require their authors to properly curate their data. Training resources should be identified specifically in support of new journal requirements on authors, editors, and reviewers.
- The draft Enabling FAIR “[FAQ document](#)” is meant to provide guidance directly to researchers on topics such as finding a data repository, data sharing, data availability statements, data citation, software citation, data submission to repositories, licensing,

linking data to publications, and general information about FAIR data and the Enabling FAIR project. Training resources should be mapped and linked to each of the areas of this FAQ document.

Process recommendations for implementation

Here we offer specific process recommendations for continuing and expanding the initial identification and mapping of RDM training resources:

- Consider using additional crowdsourcing activities to support resource identification; clarification is needed on how / with whom this could be done.
- Develop a process for receiving feedback on whether existing resources are meeting needs for implementation of FAIR by stakeholders.
 - As the Commitment Statement is agreed to and new data requirements are applied to Earth and Space Science publication processes, and repository requirements, for example, needs for new data management training will appear. This will lead to a de facto gap analysis, provided a means is developed to capture these needs effectively.
 - One avenue will be to continue to work with the DMTC, as one of the deliverables associated with a recently awarded IMLS (Institute of Museum & Library Services) National Leadership Grant is to identify, develop or adapt an “assessment framework” for the resources in the DMTC. For example, with the addition of the FAIR Data Principles to the DMTC as an educational framework, criteria for assessment could include the evaluation of how well an educational resource explains one or more of the FAIR data principles. (Note: this work is just beginning and will continue during the three year duration of the IMLS grant.)
- Help to identify and engage key liaisons to researchers (e.g., journal editors, repository managers, funding program officers - “front line”) by highlighting and /or arranging for “train the trainers” resources and events.
- Figure out where and how to continue discussions on how interested participants in TAG C efforts can support a future webinar series (such as webinars through AGU) in terms of both topics and approaches. One commonly discussed approach is to target “front line responders” (e.g. journal editors, data librarians) who interface directly with researchers needing to meet new publishing and repository requirements. Another possible approach is to provide webinars directly through researcher-targeted educational events.
- Develop strategies for continued creation, identification and mapping of educational resources to the FAIR principles and for addition to the DMTC.
 - Identify metadata experts on different metadata schemas who could help link sections or types of metadata more accurately to the FAIR principles / sub-principles.
 - Identify domain experts who could help link tasks associated with the steps of various research / data lifecycles more accurately to the FAIR principles / sub-principles.

- Identify elements from this Final Report (master document) for a document to be made available to the public, e.g., on the project website.
- Consider where / what to publish of the outcomes (perhaps after the Sept. 2018 stakeholder meeting) in order to communicate and advance FAIR data practices in the Earth and Space Sciences.

References:

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Appendices

Appendix A: Tables

Appendix A. Table 1. Invitations & reminders were sent to the following groups:

Target	Address
ESIP Data Management Training Working group	esip-dmtraining@lists.esipfed.org
ESIP Data Stewardship Committee	esip-preserve@lists.esipfed.org
ESIP overall membership list	esip-all@lists.esipfed.org
American Geophysical Union's Earth & Space Science Informatics	agu-essi@googlegroups.com
Enabling FAIR Data Stakeholders list (now RDA list:)	Sent via Shelley Stall
Geoscience information Society	Sent via Bob Tolliver
CODATA-international	codata-international@lists.codata.org
RDA-Education and Training on handling of research data Interest Group – RDA-ETHRD-ID	rda-edu-ig
DataCure	datacure@googlegroups.com
GO FAIR listserv	
Center for Open Science	Sent via Brian Nosek at COS
EarthCube	Contact the EarthCube Science Support Office (ESSO) for adding announcements to weekly newsletters.
CENDI Data Curation	cendi-data-curation@iiaweb.com
Belmont Forum e-Infrastructure and Data Management Project	seccoordgroup@bfe-inf.org
DMPonline community developer list	Sent via Stephanie Simms at CDL.
USGS Community for Data Integration Data Management Working Group	https://my.usgs.gov/confluence/display/cdi/Data+Management+Working+Group

Appendix A. Table 2a. Self-identification of crowdsource event participants:

*Indicates self-description from free text field

Participant type	Event 1	Event 2
Data professional (supporting the data processing workflow)	21	12
Data repository	16	11
Data management educator	15	9
Researcher (data creator)	14	6
Other	10	2
Research librarian	9	2
Data policymaker	5	6
Student of research data management educational content	4	0
*System architecture and software development (though I [do] not claim to have "expertise")	x	
*Coordination Officer - data management policy project	x	
*Data Curator	x	
*Data management advocate	x	
*Coordinator of community interested in data integration	x	
*Data Communication	x	
*Reproducible Research Practice Trainer	x	
*Communicator about the importance of open data/data management	x	
*Intern	x	
*Innovation Specialist	x	
*Non-profit community manager		x
*Contractor looking at RDM platforms		x

Appendix A. Table 2b. Rough identification of crowdsourcing event 2 participants (not self-identified)

Participant type	Number
Academic institutions (universities or scholarly institutes)	9
Government institution (research, data repository, researcher support, funding, policymaking)	13
Non-profit	5
Industry	2

Appendix A. Table 3. Results of Initial Identification during Crowdsourcing Event #1
Approaches = A1: Research Data Lifecycle; A2: FAIR Principles; A3: Skills Development

	A1	A2	A3	Totals (initial)	Results in DMTC
Results	26	15	37	78	TBD
Resource format / media: Animation				0	TBD
Resource format / media: Collection		1	6	7	TBD
Resource format / media: Event				0	TBD
Resource format / media: Dataset				0	TBD
Resource format / media: Interactive resource	2		6	8	TBD
Resource format / media: Moving image			2	2	TBD
Resource format / media: Presentation	8		5	13	TBD
Resource format / media: Service		1		1	TBD
Resource format / media: Software	1		9	10	TBD
Resource format / media: Sound				0	TBD
Resource format / media: Static image				0	TBD
Resource format / media: Text (including "webpage"/"website", "PDF")	15	13	9	37	TBD

Appendix B: Results of mapping activity

The “Findable” principles contain the following topics:

- F1. Globally unique and eternally persistent identifier assigned to meta(data).
- F2. Data are described with rich metadata.
- F3. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
- F4. metadata specify the data identifier.

F - Findable

Does the resource cover the following topics:

Comments / Questions on applying "F"

9 responses

This resource is for generating data management plans, so this resource may be too high-level for addressing all of these questions.

This is less of a training resource and more of a research page for users considering working with IEDA for their data needs

This is a very high level resource. It doesn't instruct on any of these elements but does mention them

<http://swcarpentry.github.io/web-data-python/06-findable/>

Some of the specific metadata guidelines are included with templates here:
<http://www.earthchem.org/data/templates>

This is a catalog of best practices that covers all stages of the Data Life Cycle and has practices relevant to each of the FAIR principles. I will explore tagging the best practices (bc they are my resource) by FAIR for easier cross referencing when creating the metadata file.

I chose yes if there was any information on a topic, even if it wasn't much.

Resource is about metadata and metadata standards

Some of these things are briefly mentioned ("should be searchable")

The “Accessible” principles contain the following topics:

A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.

A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.

A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.

A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

A - Accessible

Does the resource cover the following topics?

Comments / Questions on applying "A"

2 responses

There are a lot of parts to this overarching resource and I'm not sure if some of these should be "Yes"

all of these I am not sure of, "maybe"

The “Interoperable” principles contain the following topics:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

I - Interoperable

Does the resource cover the following topics?

Comments / Questions on applying "I"

2 responses

As above

Maybe the vocabularies follow FAIR principles, I'm not sure, I would've put "maybe"!

The “Re-usable” principles contain the following topics:

- R1. meta(data) have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
- R1.1 (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
- R2. (meta)data are associated with their provenance.
- R3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

R - Re-usable

Applies to R (Re-usable) (check all that apply)

Comments / Questions on applying "R"

7 responses

Primarily described under "Describe" and "Preserve" sections - accessibility and interoperability issues not seriously addressed here

Information about licensing is included under the "Links to Useful Resources" section.

I would've put "maybe" on R1.1 or R3

The focus of these tutorials is on complying with specific requirements for EarthChem data

No sections explicitly address these, but I think the general principles discussed are geared toward reusability.

Though this resource is about data use, there is one component about data citation

Again, resource focuses on metadata and metadata standards

General comments / questions / suggestions

19 responses

Many of the questions may not be relevant to this type of resource (DMP generator)

Hm, upon going through each of the FAIR principles for this resource, it does not seem that any are directly applicable, although I thought that things like the lesson on Data Cleaning would "help" to make reusable, interoperable data. <https://owi.usgs.gov/R/training-curriculum/intro-curriculum/Clean/> This resource is not specifically Data management related, but is data manipulation that could help with data management.

Not really a training material

This resource is not data management training. Instead, provides information about a specific data type (LIDAR)

Describes data life cycle - Primarily describes how to make data reusable under "Describe" and "Preserve" sections - accessibility and interoperability issues not seriously addressed here

This resource is new, and it does not yet include any training on FAIR principles. CyVerse does offer some information on FAIR as part of its wiki, but it has not been transferred to the Learning Center.

The resource provides top level recommendations that are organized into 10 different rules with related resources in 7 areas.

This is the second one I'm doing and I see that I am not finding as many "yeses" because I submitted resources in Event #1 that had to do with different parts of the Data Life Cycle (plan, acquire, process, analysis, preserve, publish), and the two resources I chose so far had to do with processing, which have less to do with FAIR principles (at least the way I see it). Here I checked off the domain-specific checkbox because the lessons for how to deal with data are domain-specific, this is a pretty peripheral link though!

Lots of information here, but mostly technical lessons about dealing with data at a coding level. Not quite what I had anticipated on a lifecycle map, but maybe a unique tag?

from chat w/Sophie:

1:43 PM: Hi Sophie, I only have time to do one of the resources I contributed in Session 1 – Belmont Forum open data policy & principles....this is a foundational resource, setting guidance/policy for international funding agencies (BF) to follow in funding their projects. As such it doesn't quite fit the google form in that it isn't a protocol so much as sets guidance/requirements. So I'll try as best I can but at a minimum, I hope my effort gets a review/validation as I'm not sure I'll fill out the form in a useful way (as compared to actual training resources).

A specific how-to guide for the resource more than a general data training resource. Strong focus on provenance and discovery

This is an in-person workshop, so it's impossible to evaluate online

EDI's educational resources are currently not managed according to FAIR data principles.

This resource has collected 22 different resources under 9 different areas. The values in this submission are applicable to the collection level only. Additional, individual records could be created for the 22 resources.

A lot of the information exists in this wiki, but it is not easy to find. This exercise has motivated me to go back and add some content specific to FAIR.

These resources do not address data curation - they are more about skills for using data

The National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI) provides metadata training to help data providers and data managers accomplish the goal of providing discovery-level, access-level and understanding-level metadata for their geospatial and environmental data - hard to map directly to FAIRness w/o knowing the ISO19115 info in detail!

The resource also includes IPython Notebook files for demo purposes.

Appendix C: Results of follow up survey from event #1

[Survey results link](#)

Were you able to attend all or most of the event?

7 responses

Did you get enough information in the introductory presentations to know what to do in the inputting part of the event?

6 responses

What other introductory information would have been helpful for you to have before beginning to input your findings?

3 responses

More information about EtherPad.

More about the data life cycle

Some examples would have been helpful in each of the spreadsheets to help give us a better idea what types of things you are looking for.

What did you like most about the event?

7 responses

Live, collaborative editing rather than an offline task that may have not garnered much input

Lots of energy

Having time dedicated specifically for the crowd-source sharing. Even with best intentions, people probably wouldn't have gotten around to it on their own if just given a Googlesheet to contribute to

I think it was an innovative way to get people to work together.

I thought it was great how people were able to work collaboratively without talking!

Group activity for entering candidate training materials

Live collaboration

What did you like least about the event?

3 responses

Minor technical issues when editing the Google sheet

Google Sheets got a bit unwieldy with many people editing simultaneously

I felt a bit confused at the beginning, but then got the hang of it.

Any suggestions for improvement or additional comments?

2 responses

Could we use Google chat so that we wouldn't have to switch between EtherPad and the Google doc?

Figuring out a way to keep from overwriting each other

Which future crowdsourcing events would you be interested in attending on these topics?

7 responses

What other organizations, listservs or other avenues would you suggest be contacted to expand the participation in these crowdsourcing events on RDM / Enabling FAIR Data?

3 responses

National Data Service

RDAP (not sure if they were included)

LTER information managers might be interested

Appendix D: Issues related to mapping resources to the FAIR Principles

- Many mappers found that resources covering more general RDM topics mentioned some or all of the FAIR principles at a very high level, often using different terms to discuss the principle(s), but did not provide lower level instruction on how to make the data FAIR.
- By contrast, some of the resources provided very specific instruction on generating data management plans (DMPs), on data cleaning, or on using specific tools for processing data, for examples, and so did not address the FAIR principles per se.
 - These kinds of very useful resources can be considered to apply more to one or more of the tasks associated with the steps or stages of a research lifecycle, however; and indirectly help researchers make their data FAIR, e.g., cleaning data helps make data re-usable and interoperable.
 - For future mapping documentation and activities, and for training about the FAIR principles, it would be useful to provide examples of how applying specific FAIR principles and sub-principles can help researchers understand the relationships between the abstract level of the FAIR principles and the functional tasks / processes / activities associated with RDM, using the research data lifecycle or other functional frameworks as a guide.
- Mappers found that the more familiar they were with the educational resource, the easier, faster (and probably more accurately) they were able to associate the appropriate FAIR principle /sub-principle to the resource.
- While still very useful and worthy of noting somewhere (perhaps as part of the Enabling FAIR project FAQ?), many of the resources submitted did not meet the definition of a training resource per the Selection Criteria for the DMTC. Instead, they were better considered as research guides or sources of information that should be found on a course or tutorial pathfinder, bibliography or list of references on the FAIR principles or a related topic.
- Some of the resources submitted provided instructions / explanations applicable only to specific repositories, such as how to submit data to a specific repository. Therefore, they would be less useful to a broader audience except perhaps as examples of submission documentation for other repositories. In these cases, the topics covered would be less directly understood as helping to enable FAIR data, and more directly related to either domain specific or repository specific training materials. As such, they would probably still be appropriate for submission to the DMTC and associated with a different educational framework.
- Many existing educational resources place emphasis on metadata (e.g., how to create) and metadata standards, but mapping these resources to the FAIR principles would probably be best done by those familiar with the metadata standards used, such is ISO 19115 for geospatial and environmental data.
- Several mappers who were less familiar with the resources would have preferred to have an option for “MAYBE” on the form with the assumption that the mapping would be evaluated by someone more familiar with the resource; this argues for mapping to be done at the creation phase of the resource, or more complete review of the resource by a FAIR expert.